

Decoding Multidimensional Embedding Spaces: Text-Conditioned Zero-Shot Crop Mapping

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Abstract: Earth Observation Foundation Models such as AlphaEarth encode multi-spectral, radar and geolocated text into compact embedding grids (64-d at 10 m), but cannot query its output, only raw embedding values. We show that a lightweight contrastive alignment that bridges a general-purpose LLM to the frozen AlphaEarth grid and produces text-conditioned spatial distribution maps over Hungary. We use “zero-shot” in the linguistic-generalisation sense: queries may use unseen phrasings of in-vocabulary concepts. The alignment reaches mean AUROC (Area Under Receiver Operating Curve) 0.786 on canonical class names and 0.713 on novel paraphrases, substantially above untrained random / PCA baselines (~0.5). Ablating LoRA (Low-Rank Adapter) removes 0.079 AUROC on paraphrases, isolating linguistic flexibility as LoRA's contribution.

Keywords: Earth Observation Foundation Models; zero-shot classification; crop mapping; contrastive learning; embedding alignment.

1 Introduction

Earth Observation Foundation Models (EOFMs) such as AlphaEarth (Brown et al. 2025) and TerraMind (Jakubik et al. 2025) compress multi-spectral, radar and geolocated text into dense embedding grids (64-d at 10 m for AlphaEarth). These embeddings encode rich Earth-surface semantics, yet remain opaque, and turning them into interpretable maps typically requires per-task supervised fine-tuning — negating much of the generality that makes foundation models attractive.

A bridge between free-form natural language and the frozen embedding space would let practitioners query the model for arbitrary land-cover concepts without retraining the visual encoder. Throughout this paper we use the term zero-shot in the linguistic-generalisation sense: at inference, the model accepts textual queries that share no surface tokens with any training caption and may employ unfamiliar vocabulary, terminology, or definition styles. The underlying land-cover concepts, however, are those present in the supervised training set. This is a strictly weaker claim than class-level zero-shot, which would require holding out entire classes during training, we identify the class-level setting as future work.

The objectives of this paper are: (i) to characterise the latent semantic structure of AlphaEarth's frozen 64-d embedding space with respect to agricultural land-cover classes, (ii) to design a lightweight contrastive alignment that projects free-form natural-language queries into this space, (iii) to evaluate the linguistic generalisation of the

alignment across four query categories in-vocabulary, paraphrase, compositional and distractor against simple non-trained baselines, and (iv) to characterise the conditions under which the alignment transfers and the failure modes that remain. A systematic zero-shot evaluation shows that novel phrasings unseen during training produce spatial maps with AUROC 0.71, within 0.07 of in-vocabulary performance and well above the untrained-projection baselines reported in Section 4.4.

2 Related work

AlphaEarth (Brown et al. 2025) and TerraMind (Jakubik et al. 2025) fuse multi-spectral, radar and geolocated text into transferable cell embeddings, but neither exposes a free-form natural-language query interface. CLIP-style remote-sensing models (Radford et al. 2021, Jain et al. 2025) operate at the scene level and re-encode imagery at inference. The closest prior alignment over AlphaEarth, Liu et al. (2025), targets point-of-interest categories rather than land cover. We instead align text from a general-purpose LLM directly to a frozen AlphaEarth grid, producing pixel-level distribution maps with no image re-encoding. The feasibility of such alignment is consistent with the Platonic Representation Hypothesis (Huh et al. 2024), and with evidence that modern LLM embeddings carry rich semantic structure (Petukhova et al. 2025).

3 Materials and methods

3.1 Study area and data

The study area covers Hungary on a 512×1219 grid at AlphaEarth's native 10 m resolution, ~355,000 cells remain inside the country boundary (57%). Ground truth combines CORINE Land Cover 2018 (European Environment Agency 2018, 44 thematic classes, 25 ha MMU) and Copernicus High Resolution Layer Croplands (Copernicus Land Monitoring Service 2021, wheat, maize, sunflower, rapeseed, sugar beet, ...). For each of the 46 resulting classes a normalised density map $D(c) \in [0, 1]$ over the $H \times W$ grid is computed from class occupancy. Text supervision uses CORINE class descriptions augmented with Wikipedia-sourced descriptors for lexical diversity.

3.2 Text-conditioned alignment pipeline

We construct a pipeline that projects natural-language queries into AlphaEarth's 64-d embedding space, producing text-conditioned spatial distribution maps. The text backbone is Qwen-3.5 (9B parameters) (Qwen Team 2025) with Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA, rank $r = 32$) (Hu et al. 2022) on the attention layers. The last-token hidden

state (a 4096-dimensional real vector) is extracted as the sequence representation and passed through a three-layer projection head (4096 \rightarrow 512 \rightarrow 128 \rightarrow 64, SiLU activations, layer normalisation at the input) with L2 normalisation at the output, producing a 64-dimensional unit vector aligned with the AlphaEarth embedding space.

The predicted spatial distribution (equation 1) is the cosine similarity between the text embedding and each frozen satellite cell embedding e_i :

$$s_i = \frac{\mathbf{z}_{\text{text}} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i}{\|\mathbf{z}_{\text{text}}\| \|\mathbf{e}_i\|} \quad (1)$$

3.3 Training objective

Training uses three complementary losses against $D(c)$. The primary loss (equation 2) is a density-weighted InfoNCE (van den Oord et al. 2018) in which the positive logit is the density-weighted expected cosine similarity over pixels $p \sim D(c)$, scaled by a learned temperature τ (≈ 14.9 at convergence):

$$\ell_c^+ = \mathbb{E}_{p \sim D(c)} [\text{sim}(\mathbf{z}_c, \mathbf{e}_p)] \cdot \tau \quad (2)$$

The denominator sums over negative classes with same-group masking so spectrally indistinguishable classes are not penalised (equation 3):

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{InfoNCE}} = -\log \frac{\exp(\ell_c^+)}{\exp(\ell_c^+) + \sum_{c' \notin G(c)} \exp(\ell_{c'}^+)} \quad (3)$$

A pixel-level contrastive loss samples hard negatives from the top-3 confusable classes per query, a distractor uniformity loss penalises off-topic text by minimising mean s_i^2 . Training runs 19 epochs with the satellite embeddings frozen, only the LoRA adapters and the projection head receive gradients.

3.4 Evaluation protocol

To rigorously assess zero-shot capability, we define four query buckets summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Evaluation query buckets.

Bucket	n	Purpose
A. In-vocab	20	Sanity check: queries using training class names
B. Paraphrase	16	Zero-shot linguistic: novel phrasings of known classes
C. Compositional	5	Multi-concept spatial queries
D. Distractor	10	Negative control: off-topic text

In-vocabulary queries use canonical CORINE/HRL class names. Paraphrase queries were authored by the first author and reviewed by the second author: for each of 16 selected classes spanning all major class families (crops, forests, urban, water bodies, named geographic features) we drafted alternative descriptions in three registers: everyday language, scientific or Latin terminology, and definitional encyclopaedic phrasing and retained one paraphrase per class. Compositional queries combine two concepts with a spatial relation (e.g. “vineyards near Lake Balaton”). Distractors are off-topic prompts spanning unrelated domains. The small counts ($n = 16, 5, 10$) limit statistical power and are listed in the limitations. Each

query produces a similarity map evaluated against the target class density using AUROC (positive cells: $D(c) > 0$), $\text{avg}_{\text{precision}}$, and Pearson r , computed on the Hungary-masked cells only.

3.5 Baselines

To interpret the AUROC values reported in Section 4 we compare the full pipeline against three baselines that share the frozen Qwen-3.5 backbone and the frozen AlphaEarth grid but ablate the trained alignment: (i) a random 4096 \rightarrow 64 linear projection (no training), (ii) a PCA projection fit on Qwen embeddings of the training captions, (iii) the trained projection head with LoRA disabled. All baselines are evaluated on the same 51-query set with identical metrics, reported alongside the full pipeline in Table 2.

4 Results

4.1 Embedding space structure

Before evaluating the text-conditioned pipeline, we verify that the frozen AlphaEarth embeddings already encode agriculturally relevant structure. Figure 1 shows a UMAP projection of 25,000 randomly sampled grid cells, coloured by their dominant CORINE/HRL class. Distinct clusters corresponding to cereals, forests, urban areas, and water bodies are clearly visible, confirming that the 64-d embedding space separates land-cover semantics prior to any task-specific training. This pre-existing geometry is what makes the contrastive alignment feasible: the projection head learns a mapping into an already-structured space rather than constructing semantic organisation from scratch.

Figure 1. UMAP projection of 25 k AlphaEarth grid cells (64-d \rightarrow 2D, cosine metric, $n_{\text{neighbors}} = 15$). Points are coloured by dominant CORINE/HRL class, grouped into super-categories. Land-cover clusters emerge without any task-specific training.

4.2 Linguistic generalisation and semantic precision

Using canonical class names as queries (the in-vocabulary bucket) reaches a mean AUROC of 0.786 ($\text{avg}_{\text{precision}} =$

0.725, Pearson $r = 0.334$) across 20 classes, with the highest scores on spatially extensive classes (wheat 0.93, sunflower 0.90, broad-leaved forest 0.88). The paraphrase bucket is the paper's central experiment, which utilises queries that share no surface tokens with training text, yet mean AUROC drops only to 0.713, per-class results for both buckets appear side-by-side. A subset of paraphrases outperform their in-vocabulary counterparts: “dense city centres and suburbs” (0.970) exceeds “discontinuous urban fabric” (0.930), “fields of bread grain” (0.946) surpasses “wheat” (0.931). Conversely, polysemous or factual paraphrases fail: “corn cultivation areas” (0.59 vs. 0.87 for “maize”), “grazing land for livestock” (0.31 vs. 0.70 for “pastures”), and the factual lookup “Europe's second longest river flowing through Budapest” → Danube (0.42). These findings indicate that the alignment acts as a semantic filter: it transmits language describing observable surface properties and attenuates abstract or ambiguous concepts.

4.3 Aggregate performance and baseline comparison

Table 2 summarises aggregate metrics across all buckets and contrasts the full pipeline against the three baselines defined in Section 3.5. The random projection hovers around AUROC 0.43--0.48 essentially chance, confirming that without alignment training the Qwen embeddings and the AlphaEarth grid live in unrelated subspaces. PCA on the training-caption embeddings lifts in-vocabulary AUROC to 0.588 but paraphrase performance remains near chance (0.484). The projection-head-only ablation (frozen Qwen, no LoRA) recovers most of the in-vocabulary performance (0.769 vs. 0.786) but loses around 0.08 AUROC on paraphrases (0.634 vs. 0.713), isolating LoRA as the component that delivers linguistic flexibility under unseen phrasings.

The compositional bucket drops to AUROC 0.561 because the single-dot-product similarity offers no mechanism for spatial operators such as “near” or “adjacent to”: “vineyards near Lake Balaton” collapses to vineyards globally, while “grassland around Hortobágy” (0.82) succeeds only because both components are already co-located. Off-topic distractor queries produce a mean similarity of 0.184, confirming that the uniformity loss suppresses spurious activation, though scattered hot spots (max 0.5–0.67) indicate this is a soft prior rather than a hard gate.

5 Discussion

The CORINE thesaurus uses short technical labels designed

for cartographic consistency rather than linguistic richness. The AlphaEarth backbone was pretrained on geolocated text including encyclopedic and colloquial descriptions (Brown et al. 2025), so its latent space is plausibly closer to descriptive everyday English than to the official thesaurus — consistent with the Platonic Representation Hypothesis (Huh et al. 2024). This explains why paraphrases such as “dense city centres and suburbs” outperform the training label “discontinuous urban fabric”.

5.1 Limitations

- Compositional queries involving spatial operators (near, adjacent to, around) cannot be handled by a single dot product and collapse to one component,
- Pearson r of 0.27–0.33 indicates correct ranking but absent calibration for absolute density,
- evaluation is restricted to Hungary and a single time slice,
- the paraphrase / compositional / distractor sets are small ($n = 16, 5, 10$) and authored by the same team,
- every concept evaluated here is represented in the supervised training set class-level zero-shot is left to future work,
- the distractor uniformity loss is a soft prior, not a hard gate.

6 Conclusions

We have demonstrated that frozen AlphaEarth embeddings already encode agriculturally meaningful spatial structure, and that a lightweight contrastive alignment suffices to bridge arbitrary natural-language queries to this pre-existing geometry, achieving acceptable precision on novel phrasings never encountered during training. The same alignment substantially outperforms untrained random and PCA projections of the language embeddings, and the projection-head-only ablation isolates the contribution of LoRA to linguistic flexibility under paraphrasing.

Our results reveal that the quality of text-conditioned spatial grounding depends not on whether a query was seen during training, but on the semantic precision of the query relative to the embedding space's latent structure: semantically rich paraphrases can outperform the official CORINE labels the model was trained on, while ambiguous or polysemous phrasings degrade performance. The learned alignment thus acts as a semantic filter that transmits descriptions of observable surface properties and attenuates abstract or ambiguous language. Its main limitations are a lack of spatial operators, Pearson

Table 2. Aggregate metrics by query bucket. All baselines share the frozen Qwen-3.5 backbone and the frozen AlphaEarth grid, only the alignment head differs. The trained projection head recovers most of the in-vocabulary performance even without LoRA, but LoRA contributes +0.079 AUROC on the paraphrase bucket.

Method	In-vocab AUROC	Paraphrase AUROC	Compositional AUROC	Distractor mean sim.
Random projection	0.427	0.419	0.476	-0.040
PCA projection	0.588	0.484	0.440	0.023
Projection head only (no LoRA)	0.769	0.634	0.507	0.207
Full pipeline (ours)	0.786	0.713	0.561	0.184

correlations of 0.27–0.33 that indicate the model ranks cells correctly but requires calibration for quantitative distribution estimation, and a linguistic zero-shot evaluation that does not yet cover class-level held-out concepts.

Future work includes retraining with held-out classes for class-level zero-shot evidence, geographic generalisation beyond Hungary, multi-temporal embeddings for phenology-aware queries, and per-query calibration against a uniform-prior baseline.

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7 References

- Brown, C. F., Kazmierski, M. R., Pasquarella, V. J., Rucklidge, W. J., Samsikova, M., Zhang, C., ..., Kohli, P., 2025. Alphaearth foundations: An embedding field model for accurate and efficient global mapping from sparse label data. arXiv preprint arXiv:2507.22291.
- Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, 2021. High Resolution Layer — Croplands. European Environment Agency product documentation, <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/high-resolution-layer-croplands>. (Accessed 23 May, 2026).
- European Environment Agency, 2018. CORINE Land Cover 2018 (CLC2018): Technical Guidelines. EEA technical report, <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/technical-library/clc-2018-technical-guidelines/>. (Accessed 23 May, 2026).
- Hu, E.J., Shen, Y., Wallis, P., Allen-Zhu, Z., Li, Y., Wang, S., Wang, L., Chen, W., 2022. LoRA: Low-Rank Adaptation of Large Language Models. In: International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR). arXiv:2106.09685.
- Huh, M., Cheung, B., Wang, T., Isola, P., 2024. The Platonic Representation Hypothesis. In: International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML). arXiv:2405.07987.
- Jain, P., Marcos, D., Ienco, D., Interdonato, R., Berchoux, T., 2025. TimeSenCLIP: A Time Series Vision-Language Model for Remote Sensing. arXiv:2508.11919.
- Jakubik, J., Yang, F., Blumenstiel, B., Scheurer, E., Sedona, R., Maurogiovanni, S., ..., Longépe, N., 2025. Terramind: Large-scale generative multimodality for earth observation. In: Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (pp. 7383-7394).
- Liu, J., Qin, Q., Dong, G., Wang, X., Feng, J., Zeng, Z., Cheng, T., 2025. Beyond AlphaEarth: Toward Human-Centered Geospatial Foundation Models via POI-Guided Contrastive Learning. arXiv:2510.09894.
- Petukhova, A., Matos-Carvalho, J.P., Fachada, N., 2025. Text clustering with large language model embeddings. International Journal of Cognitive Computing in Engineering 6, 100–108.
- Qwen Team, 2025. Qwen3.5: Towards Native Multimodal Agents. Technical report, <https://qwen.ai/>. (Accessed 23 May, 2026).
- Radford, A., Kim, J.W., Hallacy, C., Ramesh, A., Goh, G., Agarwal, S., Sastry, G., Askell, A., Mishkin, P., Clark, J., Krueger, G., Sutskever, I., 2021. Learning Transferable Visual Models from Natural Language Supervision. In: International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML). arXiv:2103.00020.
- van den Oord, A., Li, Y., Vinyals, O., 2018. Representation Learning with Contrastive Predictive Coding. arXiv:1807.03748.